

Report on phytochemical profile of 80 collected liverwort accessions

D2.2

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Information

Table 1 Project information

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Acknowledgement and disclaimer

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The BRYOMOLECULES project

Liverworts, an ancient group of land plants, are a rich yet underexploited source of a wide range of biologically active compounds with high potential for the bioeconomy sector as ingredients of cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals. However, their slow growth rate in nature and the consequent difficulty in obtaining large amounts of single compounds have, until now, severely hindered the in-depth exploration and exploitation of the full spectrum of activities of liverwort secondary metabolites. Recent breakthroughs in the identification of some of the genes involved in the early steps of liverwort-specific compounds suggest that, in addition to the establishment of improved methods for growth in axenic conditions, reconstruction of liverwort metabolic pathways in heterologous systems is a promising way forth towards the practical exploitation of liverwort biochemical diversity and its industrial scale up.

BRYOMOLECULES will provide actionable knowledge on European bryophyte species and their biosynthetic genes, which can be used to produce sustainable, bio-based cosmetics and pharmaceuticals ingredients for the European market.

To do so, the BRYOMOLECULES project will use a combination of the cultivation of axenic cultures and the production of the active compounds in heterologous systems to define the most suitable production platform(s) for their large-scale production. The project will achieve a very sustainable use of the chemical diversity of wild EU bryophyte species, a largely untapped source of high-added-value natural products, without significant impacts on their biodiversity.

Besides the identification of relevant lead compounds for cosmetics/cosmeceuticals and pharmaceuticals, another major impact of the project will be the production and release according to FAIR principles of a database of metabolites and biosynthetic genes of European bryophyte species that will fuel in the years to come the development of novel bio-based products based on bryophyte-derived lead compounds, according to the concept of EU valorising biodiversity for EU bioeconomy.

Project Consortium Members

Table 3 - Consortium members

<p>FONDAZIONE EDMUND MACH dal 1874</p>	Fondazione Edmund Mach (FEM)
<p>HUB INNOVAZIONE TRENTINO</p>	Fondazione HUB Innovazione Trentino (HIT) FEM LTP
<p>UNIVERSITÉ JEAN MONNET SAINT-ETIENNE</p>	Université Jean Monnet, Saint-Etienne (UJM)
<p>PAT Plant Advanced Technologies</p>	Plant Advanced Technologies PAT SA (PAT)
<p>Bionos Testing Efficiency</p>	Bionos Biotech SI (BIONOS)
<p>LUNDS UNIVERSITET</p>	Lunds Universitet (LU)
<p>UNIWERSYTET MEDYCZNY W LUBLINIE</p>	Uniwersytet Medyczny w Lublinie (UM)
<p>ESF</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF)

Summary

The Bryomolecules project set for this deliverable that the metabolomic profiles resulting from the around 40 accessions of liverworts coming from axenic culture and about 40 coming from wild-collected material will be reported and organized in a summary table that will serve in the metabolic gene identification (WP3; T3.2) and the project public database (WP3; T3.3). The report will also include conclusions on chemical diversity and chemotaxonomy of European liverworts.

This document presents a comprehensive metabolomic characterisation of 86 liverwort accessions which correspond to 36 liverwort species originating from both axenic cultures and wild-collected material within the BRYOMOLECULES project. The title of this deliverable originally referred to 80 accessions. However, the dataset was expanded to 86 because some of this samples became relevant for the research and the report reflects this updated number consistently.

Using a combination of complementary extraction strategies and advanced analytical platforms (GC–MS and LC–HRAM–MS/MS), a broad spectrum of metabolites was detected and annotated, including terpenoids, bibenzyls, bisbibenzyls, phenolic compounds, and lipid derivatives.

The dataset demonstrates high chemical diversity and strong taxon-specific metabolite patterns, supporting chemotaxonomy, bioprospecting, and downstream applications such as pathway elucidation and heterologous production.

Introduction

Liverworts (Marchantiophyta) represent one of the earliest lineages of land plants and are known for producing structurally unique and biologically active secondary metabolites. Despite this, their chemical diversity remains significantly underexplored, mainly due to limitations in biomass availability and difficulties in large-scale cultivation.

Deliverable D2.2 specifically aims to characterise the phytochemical profiles of liverwort accessions collected across Europe, thereby contributing to a broader framework linking metabolomic diversity with taxonomy, biosynthetic pathways, and biotechnological exploitation.

The results presented here complement those obtained for mosses (D2.1) and together form a comprehensive dataset describing the metabolomic landscape of European bryophytes. Importantly, this dataset is intended to feed into downstream work packages focused on gene–metabolite correlations (WP3) and heterologous production systems (WP4 and WP5).

Material and Methods

Sample material

A total of 86 liverwort accessions were analysed, including both axenic cultures (49) and wild-collected samples (37) from different European regions. Several accession of *Marchantia polymorpha* from each of the three subspecies (*polymorpha*, *ruderalis* and *montivagans*) have been included.

Extraction procedures

Samples were extracted using diethyl ether, methanol/chloroform (2:1), and methanol, applied individually or sequentially. The use of multiple solvents ensured broad metabolite coverage across polarity ranges (volatile terpenoids, lipophilic bisbibenzyls, and polar metabolites), which is essential for bryophyte metabolomics.

Liverwort samples were initially extracted with diethyl ether using a mortar. The extracts were transferred to vials, evaporated, and stored at -20°C until further analysis.

After evaporation of the ether at room temperature, the plant residues were re-extracted in a mortar using methanol/chloroform (2:1, v/v) or methanol. The extracts were transferred into 20 mL glass vials, sonicated for 20 minutes, and filtered through a $0.22\ \mu\text{m}$ PTFE syringe filter. The filtrates were then evaporated and the dried extracts were stored at -20°C until analysis.

Analytical platforms

GC–MS–EI–Q and HPLC–HRAM–MS–ESI–QToF were used for metabolomic profiling, including iterative MS/MS acquisition for improved annotation.

GC–MS–EI–Q analyses were carried out using a Shimadzu GC-2010 Plus GC instrument coupled to a Shimadzu QP2010 Ultra mass spectrometer with a single quadrupole mass analyzer and an electron impact ionisation source (Shimadzu Europa GmbH, Duisburg, Germany). Samples were injected to a fused silica capillary column ZB-5 MS (30 m, 0.25 mm i.d.) with a film thickness of 0.25 μm (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) in the split mode (1:5). Injection temperature was 250°C . Temperature program started at 50°C with 3 minutes of hold time then was increased up to 250°C with $5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ rate and 5 minutes of hold time, in the final step gradient ended at 325°C with $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ rate and 4.5 minutes of hold time with 60 minutes of total program time. Helium was used as carrier gas and its flow was set at 1.0 mL/min. MS chromatograms were acquired in scan mode with 5 minutes of solvent cut time and with scan range 40–500 amu. Ion source temperature was set at 220°C and the ionization energy was 70 eV, which is consistent with the majority of GC-MS spectra libraries. A homologous series of n-alkanes (C8–C24) were analysed under the same operating conditions in order to determine the retention time indices.

HPLC–HRAM–MS–ESI–QToF analyses were performed on Agilent 1200 Infinity HPLC chromatograph coupled to Agilent 6530B QTOF system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA,

USA) with electrospray ion source. The chromatographic separation was carried out on a Synergi Fusion RP column (2.5 μm i.d., 100 x 3 mm) supported by a suitable guard column (Phenomenex Inc, Torrance, CA, USA). The solvents system comprised of solvent A (water with 0.1% formic acid v/v) and solvent B (acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid v/v) was used in the following gradient: 20 - 60% B for 7 min, 60 - 100% B for 5 min, and 100% B for 18 min at the flow rate of 0.6 mL/min and with column temperature set at 40°C. Mass spectrometry data were collected using following parameters: nebulizer pressure of 40 psig, drying gas temp of 325°C and drying gas flow of 12 L/min, collision energies of 20 and 40 eV, sheath gas temp and flow were 325°C and 12 L/min, skimmer: 65V, capillary voltage: 4000V and fragmentor: 140V. Reference ions solution were injected into the ion source during all analysis. Total ion chromatograms were acquired in negative ionization mode using scan mode to obtain the most relevant data for metabolomic analysis. For compound identification, iterative samples were prepared and injected three times in the iterative mode using the autoMS acquisition mode. The iterative samples were prepared by mixing small aliquots from approximately 12 samples. All extracts were represented in the iterative samples.

Data processing and identification

Metabolite identification was based on a combination of spectral library matching, comparison with reference standards (when available), and interpretation of MS/MS fragmentation patterns. To ensure transparency, metabolite annotations were assigned according to standard confidence levels (MSI 1–4).

Raw LC–MS and GC–MS data were processed using MS-DIAL for deconvolution and alignment, and the resulting data matrices were subjected to log₁₀ transformation and Unit Variance (UV) scaling prior to statistical analysis. Multivariate methods, including Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA), were applied to explore metabolite patterns, identify chemotypes, and assess relationships between samples.

Due to the continuous and asynchronous acquisition of samples, analyses were conducted in consecutive batches. As a result, pooled QC samples across the full dataset were not feasible. Instead, procedural blanks were systematically included within each batch to monitor background signals and potential carryover.

Consistent analytical workflows and data processing pipelines were applied across all samples to ensure dataset comparability and robustness despite batch-wise acquisition.

Methodological limitations

During the analyses, we encountered several problems. First of all, we had to work with very small amounts of liverworts material. The second problem was related to the large variation in sample amounts, which made it impossible to prepare all samples simultaneously at the same reasonable concentration of plant material. Moreover, we also faced problems with the solubility of the obtained extracts, especially in polar solvents, which resulted in the need to use a higher percentage of mobile phase B (20%) at the beginning of the gradient program in the LC–MS

analyses. Additionally, we were unable to prepare QC samples for the liverwort GC–MS and LC–MS metabolomic analyses because the liverwort samples for extraction were delivered very late and in separate deliveries spread over time. As a result, it was not possible to prepare QC samples representative of all liverwort samples.

Limitations also include semi-quantitative data with some tentative identifications. It is primarily due to the limited and variable amounts of plant material available for metabolomic analysis, which constrained the application of absolute quantification approaches. As a result, relative signal intensities from GC–MS and LC–MS were used to compare metabolite profiles, but they do not reflect precise concentrations. In addition, a subset of metabolites was assigned as tentative identifications, based on accurate mass and fragmentation data without confirmation using reference standards, which may include structurally related compounds or isomers. Despite these limitations, the dataset remains robust and suitable for comparative metabolomics and chemotaxonomic analyses.

Results and Discussion

Metabolite diversity

The metabolomic analysis revealed that liverworts exhibit exceptionally rich and diverse secondary metabolism, considerably more complex than that observed in mosses.

The detected compounds encompass several major classes, including bisbibenzyls, bibenzyls, sesquiterpenes, diterpenoids, phenolic compounds, and primary metabolites such as sugars and lipids.

Among these, bisbibenzyls and terpenoids emerge as particularly characteristic for liverworts, forming distinctive chemical signatures that differentiate taxa at both genus and species levels.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) were performed to visualize the natural grouping, metabolic trends, and clustering patterns among the studied liverwort species.

Figure 1 shows the PCA score plot of GC–MS ether extracts, illustrating separation of samples primarily driven by volatile terpenoids as well as corresponding HCA dendrogram, confirming clustering patterns observed in PCA.

Figure 2 shows PCA for methanol–chloroform extracts after LC-MS analysis, where clustering reflects distribution of bisbibenzyls and lipid derivatives and corresponding HCA results

a. PCA

b. HCA

Figure 1. PCA (a) and HCA (b) of GC-MS ether extracts

a. PCA

b. HCA

Figure 2. PCA (a) and HCA (b) for methanol–chloroform extracts after LC-MS analysis

A key observation of this study is the strong correlation between metabolite profiles and taxonomic classification. Many genera exhibit clearly defined chemical patterns. For example, species of *Marchantia* are characterised by a rich spectrum of bisbibenzyls such as marchantins, while *Radula* species produce unique bibenzyl derivatives known as radulanins. Similarly, *Plagiochila* species are associated with plagiochilines, and *Frullania* species with sesquiterpene lactones.

These findings confirm that liverwort metabolomes provide highly reliable chemotaxonomic markers, often allowing discrimination at a finer taxonomic resolution than morphological traits alone.

The comparison of wild-collected material with axenic cultures and bioreactor-grown samples revealed that natural samples typically display the highest chemical complexity. However, cultured material still retains key diagnostic metabolites (Table 1), indicating that controlled cultivation systems can serve as viable sources of bioactive compounds.

Table 1. Chemical markers characteristic for some liverwort species from liquid cultures

<i>Trichocolea tomentella</i>	Methyl benzoates with a prenyl ether group	 Trichocolein		
<i>Pellia cf borealis</i>	Bibenzyls	 Pellepiphyllin		
<i>Plagiochila porelloides</i> and <i>P. asplenoides</i>	seco-Aromadendrane-type sesquiterpenoids	 Plagiochiline C		
<i>Frullania dilatata</i>	Eremophilanolides and eudesmanolides	 Diplophylline		
<i>Frullania tamarisci</i>	Eudesmanolides	 Diplophylline		

This observation is particularly important for the sustainable use of liverworts, as it demonstrates that biotechnological production does not necessarily compromise chemical identity.

Bioprospecting relevance

The metabolomic profiles generated in this study provide a valuable resource for bioprospecting. The presence of structurally diverse and biologically relevant compounds, such as bisbibenzyls and terpenoids, highlights several accessions as promising candidates for further investigation.

Based on chromatographic quality and metabolite richness, species such as *Pellia cf. borealis* and *Jungermannia leiantha* emerge as particularly interesting leads.

Beyond compound discovery, the dataset also supports pathway elucidation efforts by enabling the correlation of metabolite profiles with biosynthetic genes. This is essential for reconstructing liverwort metabolic pathways in heterologous systems, which represents a key objective of the project.

Contribution to WP3-WP5

The metabolomic dataset generated for liverworts provides a key input for downstream work packages by linking chemical diversity with biosynthetic and application-oriented processes.

In WP3, metabolite profiles serve as a phenotypic layer for integration with genomic and transcriptomic data, enabling the identification of biosynthetic pathways, particularly those responsible for liverwort-specific compounds such as bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls.

In WP4, the dataset supports the selection of target metabolites and pathways for heterologous production, facilitating the prioritisation of structurally diverse and industrially relevant compounds.

In WP5, the obtained profiles enable the identification of lead species and bioactive metabolites for further biological evaluation and application development in pharmaceutical and cosmetic sectors.

The use of harmonised extraction, analytical, and data processing workflows ensures interoperability across work packages and supports integration into the BRYOMOLECULES database in compliance with FAIR data principles.

Conclusion

The metabolomic analysis of 86 liverwort accessions confirms that liverworts represent one of the most chemically diverse groups among bryophytes.

The study demonstrates that:

- liverwort metabolomes are dominated by structurally unique compounds such as bibenzyls, bisbibenzyls, and specialised terpenoids,
- metabolite profiles exhibit strong taxon specificity, enabling robust chemotaxonomic classification,
- distinct chemotypes can be identified using multivariate statistical approaches.

Importantly, the dataset provides a direct link between chemical diversity and biotechnological potential, supporting:

- selection of lead species for bioprospecting,
- identification of target metabolites for pathway elucidation,
- development of heterologous production strategies.

The integration of complementary extraction methods and analytical platforms was critical for achieving broad metabolome coverage, despite inherent limitations related to sample availability and analytical constraints.

Finally, the dataset is fully aligned with the objectives of the BRYOMOLECULES project and provides a robust foundation for WP3–WP5, contributing to metabolite discovery, pathway reconstruction, and future industrial applications.

Annex 1

Metabolites were grouped into major chemical classes, including terpenoids, bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls, phenolic compounds, and lipid derivatives. This classification enabled interpretation of metabolomic profiles in a chemotaxonomic context.

Samples and corresponding metabolites whose chemical composition differs from other analyzed samples of a given species are **marked in green**.

No	Liverwort species	Sample code	Group of metabolites	Identification
1.	<i>Pellia cf borealis</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_223 X25_SW_Et_223 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_223x I26_SW_Et_223x	Terpenoids	Thujopsene β-Acoradiene Bicyclogermacrene Guaia-6,9-dien-4β-ol Globulol Nootkatene Bicycloelemene Sesquisabinene A β-Barbatene Pechueloic acid 8β-Hydroxyeremophilenolide 1,10a-dihydroxy-4,4,7,11b-tetramethyl-1,2,3,4a,5,6,6a,7,11,11a-decahydronaphtho[2,1-f][1]benzofuran-9-one Abieta-3,7-diene
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	3,4'-Dimethoxybibenzyl Pellepiphyllin (= 2-Hydroxy-3,4'-dimethoxybibenzyl)
			Phenolic compounds	1-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxy-1,2-dihydronaphthalene-2,3-dicarboxylic acid 4-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde Salicylic acid 4-Acetoxyphenol Shikimic acid
			Lipid derivatives	Undecanedioic acid (dicarboxylic fatty acid) (Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid Azelaic acid FA 18:2+3O FA 18:1+1O LPC 16:0 LPE 16:0
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol

2.	<i>Nowellia curvifolia</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_247 X25_SW_Et_247 X25_SW_MC_265 X25_SW_Et_265 I26_SW_MC_247 I26_SW_Et_247 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_262x I26_SW_Et_262x (looks like <i>Trichocolea tomentella</i>) I26_SW_MC_287x I26_SW_Et_287x	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomers 1–3) Phytol Nootkatene 7-Hydroxycostic acid (Z)-Ocimenone Isopiperitenone α -Copaene (E)- β -Caryophyllene Sesquisabinene A Germacrene D γ -Cadinene Elemol 4 α -Hydroxygermacra-1(10),5-diene α -Cadinol α -Bisabolol 8 β -Hydroxyeremophilanolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	Methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoate Trichocolein Neotomentellin 4-(3,4-Dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid Shikimic acid
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE 13-HOTrE 9-HODE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+30 Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid 3-Methyladipic acid LPE 16:0 LPC 16:0 DGMG 18:3 MGMG 16:3 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid glycosyl ester
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol (2,5) Perseitol (1,2,4) L-Asparagine (1,2) Zinniol (3 only) Geosmin (5 only)
3.	<i>Cephalozia connivens</i>	X25_SW_MC_259 X25_SW_Et_259	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Nootkatene
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE (= 9-Hydroxy-10E,12Z,15Z-octadecatrienoic acid)

				(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+30 MGMG 16:3 DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose
4.	<i>Trichocolea tomentella</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_262 X25_SW_Et_262 X25_SW_MC_305 X25_SW_Et_305 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_283x I26_SW_Et_283x (looks like different species)	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Phytol Fusicocca-3,5-diene Fusicocca-2,5-diene Nootkatene 7-Hydroxycostic acid d-Elemene cis-β-Elemene β-Elemene Bourbon-11-ene Selina-4,11-diene γ-Amorphene Bicyclogermacrene Hardwickiic acid (E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	Methyl 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzoate Trichocolein
			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-HOTrE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid FA 18:2+30 FA 18:1+10 Azelaic acid LPC 16:0 LPE 16:0 MGMG 16:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose Perseitol Sorbitol L-Asparagine Adenine
5.	<i>Fossombronia foveolata</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_283 X25_SW_Et_283 X25_SW_MC_287 X25_SW_Et_287 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_259x I26_SW_Et_259x	Terpenoids	β-Caryophyllene Guaia-6,9-diene Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Nootkatene β-Elemene α-Cubebene Isolatedene Sesquisabinene A β-Bisabolene γ-Cadinene α-Cadinol

				Unidentified DITERPENOIDS (E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde
			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Azelaic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 3-(hexopyranosyloxy)-2-hydroxypropyl ester, (9Z,12Z,15Z)- 9-HODE 9-Hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid DGMG 18:3 FA 18:1+10 FA 18:2+30 Undecanedioic acid 3-Methyladipic acid MGMG 16:3 LPC 16:0
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol L-Asparagine Adenine Geosmin
6.	<i>Jungermannia leiantha</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_309 X25_SW_Et_309 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_247x I26_SW_Et_247x	Terpenoids	Tricyclene α -Pinene Camphene β -Pinene β -Barbatene β -Acoradiene α -Neocallitropsene trans- β -Bergamotene Gymnomitr-3-en-15-ol Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) Phytol Unidentified DITERPENOIDS (E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-

			Phenolic compounds	4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde Shikimic acid 4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE 13-HOTrE 9-Hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-HODE Azelaic acid FA 18:2+3O FA 18:3+1O FA 18:4+2O Undecanedioic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid glycoside LPE 16:0 LPE 18:2 LPE 18:1 LPC 16:0 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol L-Asparagine 3-Methyladipic acid
7.	<i>Nardia scalaris</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_323 X25_SW_Et_323 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_323x I26_SW_Et_323x	Terpenoids	α-Barbatene β-Barbatene β-Acoradiene β-Chamigrene Cuparene Nootkatene Cuparophenol (Cupaophenol) 8β-Hydroxyeremophilenoide Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) ent-Kaur-16-en-15α-ol and other kauranes Phytol Unidentified diterpenoids Hardwickiic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HODE 9-HOTrE 13-HOTrE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid

				FA 18:2+30 FA 18:3+10 Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid LPE 16:0
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Adenine 3-Methyladipic acid
8.	<i>Crossocalyx hellerianus</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_325 X25_SW_Et_325	Terpenoids	Isobazzanene β-Barbatene Gymnomitrol (lub inny typu barbatane) Nootkatene Phytol
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE (Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Undecanedioic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol 3-Methyladipic acid
9.	<i>Cephalozia ambigua</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_337 X25_SW_Et_337	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) Phytol Nootkatene
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+30 Undecanedioic acid 3-Methyladipic acid
			Other compounds	Adenine Sucrose
10.	<i>Marsupella sprucei</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_339 X25_SW_Et_339 I26_SW_MC_339 I26_SW_Et_339	Terpenoids	Nootkatene Sesquisabinene A α-Humulene 8β-Hydroxyeremophilanolide Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) Phytol Manool oxide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-

			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Azelaic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid glycosyl ester LPE 18:2 LPE 18:1 LPC 16:0 LPC 18:2
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol Adenine 3-Methyladipic acid Unidentified M+ 306 (major compound)
11.	<i>Scapania nemorea</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_352 X25_SW_Et_352 Wild-collected: FR_Et_21	Terpenoids	trans- β -Bergamotene Guaia-6,9-dien-4 β -ol Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Nootkatene Sesquisabinene A β -Barbatene B Bicyclogermacrene ent-Diplophyllolide Diplophylline Dihydrodiplophylline cis-Cleroda-1,3,13-trien-16-hydroxy-15,18-dioic acid-15,16-olide cis-Cleroda-1,3,13-trien-15-hydroxy-16,18-dioic acid-16,15-olide cis-Cleroda-1,3,13-trien-15,18-dioic acid-15,16-olide 15,16-Epoxy-cis-cleroda-3,13(16),14-trien-12-hydroxy-18-oic acid-18,6 α -olide cis-Cleroda-3,13-dien-16-hydroxy-15,18-dioic acid-15,16-olide cis-Cleroda-3,13-dien-12,16-dihydroxy-15,18-dioic acid-15,16:18,6 α -diolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Lunularic acid
			Phenolic compounds	Rubiadin
			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid FA 18:3+10 FA 18:4+20 Undecanedioic acid MGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol
12.	<i>Lophocolea heterophylla</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_358 X25_SW_Et_358	Terpenoids	Nootkatene Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3)

				Phytol
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE 13-HOTrE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+3O Undecanedioic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Adenine 3-Methyladipic acid
13.	<i>Blepharostoma trichophylla</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_360 X25_SW_Et_360 I26_SW_MC_360 I26_SW_Et_360	Terpenoids	Nootkatene 8β-Hydroxyeremophilanolide Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3)
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid
			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-Trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+3O Azelaic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid glycoside LPE 18:2 LPE 18:1 LPC 16:0 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Adenine 3-Methyladipic acid
14.	<i>Cephalozia bicuspidata</i>	Liquid culture: X25_SW_MC_361 X25_SW_Et_361 I26_SW_MC_361 I26_SW_Et_361	Terpenoids	Nootkatene 8β-Hydroxyeremophilanolide Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) Phytol
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid Kaempferol-7-O-hexoside

			Lipid derivatives	9-HOTrE 13-HOTrE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:2+3O Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid glycoside LPE 18:2 LPE 18:1 LPC 16:0 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol
15.	<i>Lophozia</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_152 I26_SW_Et_152	Terpenoids	4,5-di-epi-Aristolochene Ledol 8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide Phytol
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol
16.	<i>Riccardia latifrons</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_244 I26_SW_Et_244	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomer 1) 8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 3-(hexopyranosyloxy)-2-hydroxypropyl ester, (9Z,12Z,15Z)- DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sorbitol Sucrose
17.	<i>Cephalozia lunulifolia</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_260 I26_SW_Et_260 I26_SW_MC_353 I26_SW_Et_353 Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_260x I26_SW_Et_260x	Terpenoids	8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid LPE 18:1 DGMG 18:3
			Other compounds	Sorbitol Sucrose
18.	<i>Scapania irrigua</i>	Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_265x I26_SW_Et_265x Liquid culture:	Terpenoids	Sesquisabinene A β -Barbatene Bicyclgermacrene Scapairrin I (<i>tentative</i>)

		I26_SW_MC_308 I26_SW_Et_308		8β-Hydroxyeremophilenolide Hardwickiic acid Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Neophytadiene (isomer 2) Neophytadiene (isomer 3) Phytol (E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol
19.	<i>Frullania dilatata</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_266 I26_SW_Et_266 I26_SW_MC_304 I26_SW_Et_304 I26_SW_MC_336 I26_SW_Et_336 Wild-collected FR_Et_17	Terpenoids	α-Humulene Bicyclogermacrene Drimenol Dihydrocostunolide Costunolide β-Cyclocostunolide Dihydrofrullanolide Frullanolide 8β-Hydroxyeremophilenolide Dilatanolide A Dilatanolide B Spirodilatanolide B Diplophylline Hardwickiic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	2-Geranylo-3,5-dihydroxybibenzyl Bibenzyl (Saccatene C) Perrottetin E
			Phenolic compounds	Apigenin Luteolin 3',4',5,7-Tetrahydroxyflavone Kaempferol-7-O-hexoside Luteolin-7,3'-di-O-glucoside Rubiadin
			Lipid derivatives	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:3+10 Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol
20.	<i>Plagiochila porelloides</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_270 I26_SW_Et_270 Wild-collected FR_Et_20	Terpenoids	Maali-1,3-diene β-Barbatene Maalian-5-ol 8β-Hydroxyeremophilenolide Plagiochilide

				<p>Plagiochiline A Plagiochiline C Plagiochiline H Diplophylline ent-Diplophyllolide Fusicocca-3,5-dien</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Bibenzyl (Saccatene C)
			Phenolic compounds	4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid
			Lipid derivatives	<p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:4+20 FA 18:3+10 Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid</p>
			Other compounds	<p>Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol Malic acid</p>
21.	<i>Plagiochila asplenoides</i>	<p>Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_271 I26_SW_Et_271 Wild-collected FR_Et_10</p>	<p>Terpenoids</p>	<p>β-Barbatene Bicyclgermacrene Maalian-5-ol 8β-Hydroxyeremophilenolide Plagiochilide Plagiochiline A Plagiochiline B Plagiochiline C Plagiochiline H</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	<p>Lunularic Acid Perrottetin E isomer Bis(Bibenzyl) isomer 3 of C28H22O5 Bis(Bibenzyl) isomer 4 of C28H22O5 Bis(Bibenzyl) isomer 9 of C28H22O5 Bibenzyl (Saccatene C)</p>
			Phenolic compounds	Fuegin
			Lipid derivatives	<p>Azelaic acid 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:3+10 MGMG 18:3 LPC 18:3 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3</p>
			Other compounds	Sucrose
22.	<i>Lophozia silvicola</i>	<p>Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_295 I26_SW_Et_295</p>	<p>Terpenoids</p>	<p>Eudesma-4(15),11-dien 8-one Eudesma-4(15),7(11)-dien 8-one 8b-Hydroxyeremophilenolide</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-

			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sorbitol Sucrose
23.	<i>Gymnocola inflata</i>	Bioreactors: I26_SW_MC_309x I26_SW_Et_309x	Terpenoids	Tricyclene α -Pinene Camphene β -Pinene α -Funebrene β -Funebrene β -Acoradiene α -Neocallitropsene trans- β -Bergamotene Gymnomitr-3-en-15-ol 8 β -Hydroxyeremophilanolide Diterpenoids (clerodane-type) Hardwickiic acid (E)-5-[(1S,8aS)-5,5,8a-trimethyl-2-methylidene-3,4,4a,6,7,8-hexahydro-1H-naphthalen-1-yl]-3-(hydroxymethyl)-2-oxopent-3-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	9-HODE 9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid FA 18:3+10 Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol
24.	<i>Radula complanata</i>	liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_315 I26_SW_Et_315 XI24_SW_MC_137 XI24_SW_Et_137 Wild-collected: FR_Et_16	Terpenoids	8 β -Hydroxyeremophilanolide 9,11(13)-eremophiladien-12-oic acid α -Santalene β -Santalene Sesquisabinene B β -Acoradiene Phytol Gelomulide N (diterpenoid)
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	3-Methoxybibenzyl 3-Hydroxy-4,5-methylenedioxybibenzyl 3,4'-Dimethoxybibenzyl 3,5-dihydroxy-2-(3-methyl-2-butenyl)bibenzyl Bibenzyl (Saccatene C) Radulanin A Radulanin I Radulanin L Perrottetin E
			Phenolic compounds	Trihydroxyflavone C-hexoside C-pentoside

				Trihydroxyflavone O-hexoside C-pentoside Linear diarylheptanoid (platyphyllenone isomer)
			Lipid derivatives	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:3+10 MGMG 18:3 LPC 18:3 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3 Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Perseitol (2R)-Isopropenyl-6-hydroxy-4-(2-phenylethyl)dihydrobenzofuran
25.	<i>Lophozia longidens</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_317 I26_SW_Et_317	Terpenoids	Bicycloelemene Aristolene Calarene b-Barbatene b-Acoradiene Bicyclogermacrene
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose
26.	<i>Mylia anomala</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_327 I26_SW_Et_327	Terpenoids	Neophytadiene (isomer 1) Fusicocca-3,5-diene Phytol
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol
27.	<i>Frullania dilatata</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_336 I26_SW_Et_336 I26_SW_MC_304 I26_SW_Et_304 Wild-collected FR_Et_17	Terpenoids	Dilatanolide A Dilatanolide B Spirodilatanolide B Dihydrofrullanolide Frullanolide β -Cyclocostunolide 8 β -Hydroxyeremophilanolide Diplophylline Drimenol Hardwickic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	2-Geranylo-3,5-dihydroxybibenzyl Bibenzyl (Saccatene C) Perrottetin E

			Phenolic compounds	Apigenin Luteolin 3',4',5,7-Tetrahydroxyflavone Kaempferol-7-O-hexoside Luteolin-7,3'-di-O-glucoside Rubiadin
			Lipid derivatives	9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:3+10 Azelaic acid Undecanedioic acid
			Other compounds	Sucrose Sorbitol Perseitol
28.	<i>Bazzania trilobata</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_340 I26_SW_Et_340	Terpenoids	trans-Calamenene trans-2-Hydroxycalamenene cis-2-Hydroxycalamenene 8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 3-(hexopyranosyloxy)-2-hydroxypropyl ester, (9Z,12Z,15Z)-
			Other compounds	Sucrose
29.	<i>Frullania tamarisci</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_356 I26_SW_Et_356	Terpenoids	Dihydrofrullanolide Frullanolide Diplophylline 8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	-
			Lipid derivatives	Azelaic acid LPC 18:2
			Other compounds	Sucrose
30.	<i>Blepharostoma trichophylla</i>	Liquid culture: I26_SW_MC_360 I26_SW_Et_360	Terpenoids	8b-Hydroxyeremophilanolide Azelaic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Zinniol 4-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-6,7-dihydroxynaphthalene-2-carboxylic acid
			Phenolic compounds	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 3-(hexopyranosyloxy)-2-hydroxypropyl ester, (9Z,12Z,15Z)-
			Lipid derivatives	(hexopyranosyloxy)-2-hydroxypropyl ester, (9Z,12Z,15Z)-
			Other compounds	LPE 18:2 LPE 18:1 LPC 16:0 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3 Sucrose

				Sorbitol
31.	<i>Lophozia longiflora</i>	Liquid culture: X124_SW_MC_152 X124_SW_Et_152	Terpenoids	<p>α-Pinene Globulol Patchulane 1,6-Heptadiene, 2,5,5-trimethyl- 2,6-Octadiene, 2,6-dimethyl- 2-Hexene, 3,5,5-trimethyl- 9,11(13)-Eremophiladien-12-oic acid Gelomulide N trans-Geranylgeraniol (E,E,E)-3,7,11,15- Tetramethylhexadeca-1,3,6,10,14-pentaene Phytol</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	<p>Caffeic acid Esculetin Isorhamnetin 3-O-glucoside 2-Hydroxyquinoline</p>
			Lipid derivatives	<p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid Azelaic acid cis-10-Heptadecenoic acid cis-13-Eicosenoic acid Palmitoleic acid γ-Linolenic acid 4,7,10,13,16,19-Docosahexaenoic acid methyl ester 5,8,11,14,17-Eicosapentaenoic acid methyl ester 5,8,11,14-Eicosatetraenoic acid methyl ester 6-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester 8,11-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid methyl ester 9,12-Octadecadienoic acid ethyl ester Hexadecanoic acid methyl esters (various) Hexadecanoic acid tetradecyl ester 1-Hexacosanol n-Tetracosanol-1 Octacosanol Octacosyl acetate</p>
			Other compounds	<p>β-Amyrin β-Sitosterol Campesterol Stigmasterol Stigmasteryl acetate 9,19-Cyclolanost-24-en-3-ol acetate γ-Tocopherol Vitamin E Squalane</p>

				<p>(Z,Z)-3,6-Nonadienal 13-Tetradecenal 7-Hexadecenal E-14-Hexadecenal Octadecanal Heptanal Nonanal 2,4-Dodecadienal 2,4-Undecadienal 2-Undecanone, 6,10-dimethyl- Undecane, 2-methyl- Eicosane, 10-methyl- Heptadecane, 3-methyl- Hexadecane, 7-methyl- 4-Methyl-docosane Cyclohexadecane Cyclodecanol Cyclohexane derivatives 9,12,15-Octadecatrien-1-ol (R)-(-)-(Z)-14-Methyl-8-hexadecen-1-ol Malic acid 17-Octadecynoic acid 1-Docosene 1-Octadecene (E,Z)-2,4-Dodecadiene Valeric anhydride</p>
32.	<i>Diplophyllum albicans</i>	Wild-collected FR_Et_11	Terpenoids	<p>Anastreptene cis-β-Elementene β-Acoradiene Selina-4,11-diene 1(10)-Spirovetivene-7β-ol Eudesm-3-ene-6,7-oxide Diplophylline Dihydrodiplophylline ent-Diplophyllolide</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	-
			Phenolic compounds	Rubiadin
			Lipid derivatives	<p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid FA 18:3+10 Undecanedioic acid MGMG 18:3 LPC 18:3 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3</p>
			Other compounds	<p>Malic acid Sorbitol Perseitol</p>
33.	<i>Porella cordaeana</i>	Wild-collected FR_Et_18	Terpenoids	<p>Pinguisanine 1,10a-dihydroxy-4,4,7,11b-tetramethyl-1,2,3,4a,5,6,6a,7,11,11a-decahydronaphtho[2,1-f][1]benzofuran-9-one</p>

				(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Lunularic acid 3-Methoxybibenzyl Bibenzyl (Saccatene C) Perrottetin E (isomer)
			Phenolic compounds	Trihydroxyflavone C-hexoside C-pentoside Trihydroxyflavone O-hexoside C-pentoside Lactarorufin B isomer 1 Lactarorufin B isomer 2 Rubiadin Fuegin
			Lipid derivatives	(Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Undecanedioic acid Methyl palmitate MGMG 18:3 LPC 18:3 LPC 18:2 DGMG 18:3 PI 34:2
			Other compounds	Malic acid
34.	<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> <i>subsp. polymorpha</i>	Cultivation under non-axenic conditions on pot soil in a climate chamber: I26_SW_MC_BV1A I26_SW_Et_BV1A I26_SW_MC_BR4 I26_SW_Et_BR4 I26_SW_MC_MPP I26_SW_Et_MPP I26_SW_MC_2 I26_SW_Et_2 I26_SW_MC_6 I26_SW_Et_6 I26_SW_MC_11 I26_SW_Et_11 I26_SW_MC_13 I26_SW_Et_13 I26_SW_MC_16 I26_SW_Et_16 I26_SW_MC_28 I26_SW_Et_28	Terpenoids	Isoledene β-Elemene α-Gurjunene β-Barbatene 5-epi-Aristolochene 4,5-diepi-Aristolochene Germacrene D Selina-4,11-diene β-Selinene α-Selinene Eremophilene Isobazzanene β-Funebrene α-Cuprenene δ-Cuprenene γ-Cuprenene Cuparene Cubebol Cyclopropanecuparenol epi-Cyclopropanecuparenol Cuparane-type alcohol Viridiflorol Ledol Palustrol Cyclomytayan-15-ol Neophytadiene (isomer 1)
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Lunularin Prelunularic acid Lunularic acid

				<p>Marchantin A (including isomers 1–5) Marchantin H Marchantin G Marchantin E Perrottetin E Bis(bibenzyl) isomer groups: C28H24O4 (multiple isomers) C28H24O6 (multiple isomers) C28H22O5 (multiple isomers) C28H22O7 (multiple isomers) C29H26O6</p>
			Phenolic compounds	<p>Luteolin Apigenin Baicalin (+ isomers) Trihydroxyflavone isomers (1–4) Trihydroxyflavone hexoside</p>
			Lipid derivatives	-
			Other compounds	Malic acid
35.	<p><i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> <i>subsp. ruderalis</i></p>	<p>Wild-collected: PL_Et_MPIt PL_MC_MPIt PL_M_MPEX Cultivation under non-axenic conditions on pot soil in a climate chamber: I26_SW_MC_MPR I26_SW_Et_MPR I26_SW_MC_3 I26_SW_Et_3 I26_SW_MC_4 I26_SW_Et_4 I26_SW_MC_5 I26_SW_Et_5 I26_SW_MC_7 I26_SW_Et_7 I26_SW_MC_8 I26_SW_Et_8 I26_SW_MC_15 I26_SW_Et_15 I26_SW_MC_25 I26_SW_Et_25 I26_SW_MC_26 I26_SW_Et_26</p>	<p>Terpenoids</p>	<p>Thujopsene β-Barbatene β-Chamigrene β-Acoradiene β-Microbiotene Myltayl-4(12)-ene Selina-4,11-diene Isobazzanene α-Neocallitropsene Cuparene α-γ-/δ-Cuprenene Cyclopropanecuparenol epi-Cyclopropanecuparenol Thujopsane-2β-ol Thujopsenone ent-9-oxo-α-Chamigrene β-Herbertenol Cuparophenol Microbiotol Atractylenolide III</p>
			Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	<p>Lunularin Lunularic acid Prelunularic acid Marchantin A (+ isomers 1–5) Marchantin Marchantin G Marchantin E Multiple bis(bibenzyl) isomers: C28H24O4 C28H24O6 C28H22O5 C28H22O7 Perrottetin E (+ isomers) Perrottetin F</p>
			Phenolic compounds	<p>Luteolin Apigenin Eriodictyol</p>

				<p>Diosmetin Tricetin 3',4',5,7-Tetrahydroxyflavone 3,7,4'-Trihydroxyflavone Kaempferol 3-glucuronide Quercetin 3-O-glucuronide Trihydroxyflavone isomers Trihydroxyflavone hexoside Baicalin (+ isomers) 4-Hydroxybenzaldehyde Salicylic acid 5-Methoxysalicylic acid p-Coumaric acid</p>
			Lipid derivatives	<p>9-hydroxy-10,12-octadecadienoic acid 13-HOTrE (Z)-5,8,11-trihydroxyoctadec-9-enoic acid Suberic acid Azelaic acid Pimelic acid Decanedioic acid Undecanedioic acid Tridecanedioic acid Hydroxysebacic acid LPC 18:3 DGMG 18:3</p>
			Other compounds	<p>Malic acid</p>
36.	<p><i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> <i>subsp. montivagans</i></p>	<p>Cultivation under non-axenic conditions on pot soil in a climate chamber: I26_SW_MC_MPM I26_SW_Et_MPM I26_SW_MC_12 I26_SW_Et_12 I26_SW_MC_14 I26_SW_Et_14 I26_SW_MC_17 I26_SW_Et_17 I26_SW_MC_18 I26_SW_Et_18 I26_SW_MC_20 I26_SW_Et_20 I26_SW_MC_22 I26_SW_Et_22 I26_SW_MC_23 I26_SW_Et_23 I26_SW_MC_24 I26_SW_Et_24 I26_SW_MC_27 I26_SW_Et_27</p>	Terpenoids	<p>Isoledene β-Elemene α-Gurjunene β-Barbatene 5-epi-Aristolochene 4,5-diepi-Aristolochene Germacrene D Selina-4,11-diene β-Selinene α-Selinene Eremophilene Isobazzanene β-Funebrene β-Chamigrene Myltayl-4(12)-ene α-Cuprenene β-/γ-/δ-Cuprenene Cuparene Cubebol Cyclopropanecuparenol epi-Cyclopropanecuparenol Cuparane-type alcohol Viridiflorol Cyclomyltaylan-15-ol Thujopsene Thujopsenone Thujopsane-2β-ol Neophytadiene (isomer 1)</p>

	Bibenzyls and bisbibenzyls	Lunularin Prelunularic acid Lunularic Acid Marchantin A (including isomers 1–5) Marchantin G Marchantin H Marchantin E Perrottetin E Multiple bis(bibenzyl) isomers: C28H24O4 isomers C28H24O6 isomers C28H22O5 isomers C28H22O7 isomers C29H26O6 isomers
	Phenolic compounds	Luteolin Apigenin Baicalin (+ isomers) Trihydroxyflavone isomers (1–4) Trihydroxyflavone hexoside
	Lipid derivatives	-
	Other compounds	Malic acid

